

How can I make my research data...

Findable?

- **Publish your data** – use a searchable repository that provides a persistent identifier, e.g. a DOI. You can select one via the [WUR Repository Finder](#).
- **Enrich your data with metadata** – use the standard of the repository and provide detailed information about the project and samples so the data is findable in search queries.
- **Register your data in Pure** – Pure is the research information system behind [Research@WUR](#). Send an email to data@wur.nl with the DOI for the data and the accompanying article.

Accessible?

- **Determine if your data can be shared** - use the [WUR research data sharing guidelines](#) to determine what level of access is appropriate for your data.
- **For non-sensitive data, make it open access** – publish data openly in an easy-to-access repository that supports efficient and quick data retrieval.
- **For sensitive data, allow access requests** – publish the metadata so your research is findable, and provide instructions for how to request access (when possible).

Interoperable?

- **Publish files in open formats** – provide files in [preferred \(open\) formats](#) that don't require specific software to access or analyse.
- **Use common terms** – use standard formats, languages, and terms that are common within and across disciplines.
- **If needed, provide a codebook** – when abbreviations or uncommon language is needed, define these terms in a [codebook](#) that accompanies your research data. This allows other researchers to decode information in your files.

Reusable?

- **Release your research data and/or metadata with a licence** – make the terms of re-use clear via a [licence](#) that indicates if (and how) data can be re-used. For restricted or closed access data, a custom licence published with your metadata can be used.
- **Include a README file** – describe the origin and owner(s) of the data, and as much relevant information as possible through a [README file](#). Try to include the who, what, where, when, why, and how, of your research to tell the story behind your data.